

Review

Integrated digestate management: Contaminant control, valorisation and circular pathways

Vera Proskynitopoulou^{a,*}, Anastasios Vourros^a, Ioannis Garagounis^a,
Souzana Lorentzou^a, Anastasios Zouboulis^b, Kyriakos Panopoulos^a

^a ARTEMIS Laboratory, Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute, Centre for Research & Technology Hellas (CERTH), 6th Km Charilaou-Thermi Road, Themi, 57001, Thessaloniki, Greece

^b Laboratory of Chemical & Environmental Technology, Department of Chemistry, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Digestate
Nutrient recovery
Membrane treatment
Waste valorisation
Circular economy
Contaminant removal

ABSTRACT

Digestate management is essential to both environmental protection and sustainable agriculture. However, its safe and effective agricultural use is increasingly challenged by strong variability in composition and the presence of persistent contaminants, including heavy metals, pharmaceuticals, microplastics and per- and poly-fluoroalkyl substances. While numerous treatment and recovery technologies have been developed, existing research remains fragmented, often addressing individual contaminants or processes without a unified framework linking environmental risk, technological performance and system-level decision-making. This review systematically synthesizes current knowledge on digestate characteristics, contaminant profiles and treatment technologies, with particular emphasis on nutrient recovery, contaminant control and circular valorisation pathways. Conventional, advanced and emerging technologies are critically compared across Technology Readiness Levels, highlighting trade-offs between recovery efficiency, contaminant fate, energy demand and the generation of secondary waste streams. The analysis reveals that many widely applied technologies primarily redistribute contaminants into concentrated side streams, underscoring the need for integrated treatment trains that combine separation, recovery and destructive steps. Building on this synthesis, the review proposes a structured decision framework that links digestate composition and management objectives with appropriate technology combinations, explicitly integrating techno-economic feasibility, environmental performance and technology maturity. This framework provides a practical tool for selecting and designing digestate valorisation strategies tailored to feedstock characteristics and regulatory constraints. Finally, critical research gaps and policy needs are identified to support the transition toward environmentally safe, economically viable and circular digestate management systems.

1. Introduction

The management of digestate, a residue that is produced from anaerobic digestion processes, stands as a critical aspect in the fields of waste management and sustainable agriculture. The characteristics of digestate are not uniform and are strongly influenced by factors such as the type of organic materials used as feedstock in the digester and the specific anaerobic digestion techniques employed (Wang and Lee, 2021). These variations can significantly impact the suitability of digestate for agricultural applications (Karimi et al., 2022; Nkoa, 2014). Numerous studies have reported that organic wastes' digestion, can

introduce complexities related to impurities like pharmaceuticals (Ali et al., 2019; Boix et al., 2016), heavy metals and plastics (Bünemann et al., 2024). These impurities pose environmental risks, particularly when digestate is applied to agricultural land, necessitating thorough treatment processes to ensure safety and sustainability (Bünemann et al., 2024).

Effective valorisation of digestate requires a shift from conventional disposal or land spreading toward integrated management strategies that maximize nutrient and carbon recovery while mitigating contaminants (Wang and Lee, 2021). Depending on feedstock composition and digestate characteristics, a wide range of recovery options is available

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: verapros@certh.gr (V. Proskynitopoulou), avourros@certh.gr (A. Vourros), garagoun@certh.gr (I. Garagounis), souzana@certh.gr (S. Lorentzou), zoubouli@chem.auth.gr (A. Zouboulis), panopoulos@certh.gr (K. Panopoulos).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2026.129629>

Received 27 October 2025; Received in revised form 14 February 2026; Accepted 7 April 2026

Available online 12 April 2026

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(Vaneckhaute et al., 2017). Mechanical separation can yield solid fractions suitable for soil amenders (Beggio et al., 2022), while liquid fractions can be concentrated into nutrient-rich fertilizers (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024c). Chemical and thermal processes can generate struvite (Urbanowska et al., 2023), ammonium salts (Carucci et al., 2022), or hydrochars (Oliveira et al., 2026), whereas biological treatments, including composting can enhance organic carbon recovery (Czekala et al., 2023). These pathways allow the production of diverse end-products, fertilizers, soil amenders, and water, enabling tailored strategies that meet agronomic, industrial, or local market needs. Integration of these processes, often in multi-step treatment trains, provides flexibility for stakeholders to optimize both resource efficiency and environmental performance based on available infrastructure, energy inputs, and desired product portfolio.

Alongside technological advancements, regulatory frameworks play a crucial role in governing the production, use, and trade of digestate. Within the European Union (EU), directives such as the Waste Framework Directive (“Directive, 2008/98/EC,” 2008), Animal By-Products Regulation (“Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009,” 2009), Fertilizers Regulation (“Regulation (EU) 2019/1009,” 2019), Nitrates Directive (“Directive 91/676/EEC,” 1991), and Sewage Sludge Directive (“Directive 86/278/EEC,” 1986) provide guidelines on manufacturing processes, quality standards, and environmental considerations. While these regulations aim to ensure safe digestate handling and promote environmentally friendly practices, challenges persist due to differences in implementation across member states. Despite efforts to encourage the use of recycled organic fertilizers and mitigate environmental risks, disparities remain, impacting market access and regulatory adherence.

While significant progress has been made in understanding digestate characteristics, treatment technologies and regulatory frameworks, existing research remains largely structured along separate technological, environmental, and regulatory lines. Studies and reviews typically focus either on individual treatment options or on specific contaminant groups with limited integration between digestate composition, contaminant risks and technology performance. Emerging contaminants of increasing regulatory concern, notably polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) and antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs), remain insufficiently addressed in digestate-focused assessments, despite evidence of their persistence through anaerobic digestion and post-treatment processes. In addition, treatment technologies are often evaluated without explicit consideration of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), energy demand, secondary waste generation, or compatibility with downstream valorisation pathways, reducing their usefulness for full-scale implementation under real-world constraints. Consequently, structured guidance linking feedstock characteristics, contaminant profiles, treatment objectives and technology selection is still lacking, particularly in the context of tightening environmental regulation and increasing demand for nutrient recycling. To address these limitations, this paper provides an integrated and critical synthesis of digestate characteristics, contaminant profiles and treatment and recovery technologies across conventional, advanced and emerging approaches and translates this synthesis into a decision framework that links digestate properties and management objectives with appropriate treatment and valorisation pathways, accounting for contaminant fate, nutrient recovery performance, techno-economic feasibility and TRL.

2. Methodology

The methodology of this review is based on a structured narrative literature analysis focusing on digestate characteristics, contaminant profiles and treatment and valorisation technologies relevant to sustainable agriculture and circular economy applications. Peer-reviewed articles were primarily retrieved from the Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar to capture recent and emerging studies. The literature search employed combinations of keywords including “digestate”, “digestate treatment”, “digestate valorisation”, “emerging

contaminants”, “pharmaceuticals”, “antibiotics”, “PFAS”, “microplastics”, “nutrient recovery”, “membrane processes” and “thermal treatment”. Studies were selected based on their relevance to digestate composition, environmental risks, contaminant fate, and technological performance, with emphasis on works published in the last 5-10 years. Articles were excluded if they focused exclusively on biogas production without addressing digestate, lacked quantitative or mechanistic insight, or were not directly applicable to agricultural or environmental management contexts. Additional key references were identified through backward and forward citation tracking. The selected literature was critically analysed and synthesised to identify common trends, knowledge gaps and TRLs, forming the basis for the comparative assessment and decision framework presented in this review.

3. Overview of digestate characteristics and challenges

3.1. Digestate composition and variability

The characteristics of digestate vary based on the type of waste fed into the digester and operational parameters of the anaerobic digestion (AD) reactor (Sheets et al., 2015). pH characteristics of digestate typically range from 7 to 8.5, maintaining a slightly alkaline environment that increases with ammonia accumulation and volatile fatty acid (VFA) degradation, while decreasing during carbonate and phosphate precipitation or VFA accumulation (Drosg et al., 2015). Total Solids (TS) content varies widely (1 to 25 %) due to the variability in biodegradability of input substrates, with higher TS content resulting from lignocellulosic substrates and low digestibility, typical of agricultural residues (Drosg et al., 2015). Digestates from easily biodegradable substances exhibit lower TS content and Volatile solids/Total Solids ratio (VS/TS) (Barampouti et al., 2020). For example, poultry litter and cattle manure exhibit lower biodegradability compared to pig slurry due to their higher proportion of lignified compounds derived from cereal straw and sawdust (Iocoli et al., 2019). Consequently, AD of biomass with low fiber content produces minimal digestate (Luste et al., 2012), whereas biomass with high fiber content (such as wheat straw) yields digestate with lower water content (Negri et al., 2016).

During the anaerobic process, elements undergo transformation from organic form to inorganic. For example, organic nitrogen degradation leads to ammonium accumulation, particularly from protein and amino acid content, contributing significantly to total nitrogen content. The digestate from pig manure typically contains around 80 % of the total nitrogen in the form of ammonium, primarily due to the hydrolysis of urea and the mineralization of organic nitrogen in pig slurry, leading to significant ammonium release (Pampillón-González et al., 2017). Food-based digestate also generally exhibits higher nitrogen content and yields greater methane production than digestate derived from animal waste (such as cattle and pigs) (Nicholson et al., 2005). Furthermore, organic phosphorus is converted into orthophosphate during AD, with 90 % of phosphate interacting and precipitating with magnesium and calcium cations, consequently increasing phosphorus concentration in the solid fraction (Christensen et al., 2009; Fricke et al., 2007).

High concentrations of other minerals are also reported in digestates, primarily influenced by digestate’s feedstock. Crop digestate, for instance, is characterized by high concentrations of biologically available potassium, which enhances agricultural product quality, soil physical properties, and plant disease resistance (Römheld and Kirkby, 2010). Moreover, high salt content, such as sodium and chloride concentrations, has been outlined in several studies on digestate derived from pig manure (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024c) and mixed food waste (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024). While the latter can enhance crop yields and biomass, excessive application to young plants can be detrimental (Katerji et al., 2003; Nkoa, 2014).

3.2. Emerging contaminants in digestate

Different feedstocks in the AD plants carry different impurities and contaminants that can end up in the digestate in unaltered or in modified forms. Indicatively, although AD of swine slurry effectively eliminates most pathogens, faecal coliform bacteria levels remain high, necessitating post-treatment of the effluent (Nicholson et al., 2005). Seeds, pathogens, and biomolecules, may be neutralized by a pre-pasteurization step (around 70 °C for approximately 1 h) or degraded by the digestion process itself, especially if it is a thermophilic (Drosg, 2013). For instance, research suggests that an AD treatment of 10 h or more at a temperature of at least 52 °C can achieve the same sanitation effect as 1 h at 70 °C (Angelidaki and Ellegaard, 2003).

Heavy metals in feedstocks, particularly organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) containing elevated lead, nickel, chromium, and mercury, remain largely unchanged during AD (Castro et al., 2017). Consequently, metal-contaminated substrates produce digestates with high heavy metal concentrations potentially unsuitable for agricultural use, necessitating proper feedstock segregation to maintain compliance levels.

Organic molecules (e.g. carbohydrates, lipids and proteins), when fed to anaerobic digesters, can be broken down into smaller ones, eventually being converted into biogas. However, some cannot be digested within typical retention times (Ali et al., 2019; Boix et al., 2016; Gurmessa et al., 2020; Sanz et al., 2021). Many of these persistent compounds are toxic and degrade slowly in the environment and organisms, accumulating through bioaccumulation to harmful levels in animals and humans even when environmental concentrations are low (Sedi et al., 2010).

Furthermore, it is well established that a significant portion of drugs (e.g. antibiotics and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs) either used by humans or administered to animals is excreted in the sewers/sewage sludge or in the manure respectively, threatening aquatic species and ecosystems (Ezzariai et al., 2018; M. J. Liu et al., 2020). Due to the resilient nature of antibiotics, their degradation during AD of livestock manure and sewage sludge remains unsatisfactory, with removal efficiencies ranging from 40 % to 77 % (Oberoi et al., 2019). Some antibiotics undergo limited structural changes post-AD, implying that the transformed products may remain active (Spielmeyer, 2018). Consequently, residual antibiotics are often discharged with the digestate, predominantly in its liquid fraction, which constitutes 90 % to 95 % of the digestate (G. Yang et al., 2022). Therefore, the direct use of liquid fraction of digestate as fertilizer results in the accumulation of remaining antibiotics and their active by-products in the soil environment, fostering the increase of ARGs and antibiotic-resistant bacteria (Sanz et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2020).

Other studies on contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) in digestates found octocrylene and acetaminophen in liquid digestates and tris(chloropropyl) phosphate (TCPP) in the solid fraction of digestates (Ali et al., 2019). Golovko et al. identified 48 CECs in digestates, with the highest levels for pyroxydine, caffeine, theobromine, and nicotine (Golovko et al., 2022). It is worth noting that despite extensive and optimized AD, the presence of CECs in digestate samples suggests that adjustments to the treatment process's operational conditions are necessary to minimize CEC contamination (Ali et al., 2019).

Polychlorinated dibenzodioxins (PCDDs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), even though regulated for decades, can still be found in environmental samples (Beníšek et al., 2015; Brändli et al., 2007; Wei et al., 2023). Newer substances like brominated flame retardants (BFRs) and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) (eternal chemicals) are now drawing regulatory attention (Bünemann et al., 2024). PFAS have been reported in digestates, reflecting their strong sorption to sewage sludge and other organic feedstocks such as food waste (Johansson Mäcs Irmalinn Nilsson Examiner et al., 2025). While primary sludge tends to be enriched in long-chain compounds such as perfluorodecanoate (PFDA), digestates

from blended primary and waste-activated sludge typically contain both short- and long-chain homologues (Lakshminarasimman et al., 2021). Conventional AD processes have demonstrated only limited effectiveness in reducing PFAS loads, with most studies reporting modest removals (<40 %), and in some instances, the biotransformation of precursors under strictly anaerobic conditions has resulted in the formation of additional perfluoroalkyl acids (Arvaniti et al., 2024; Lakshminarasimman et al., 2021). The persistence of PFAS in stabilized biosolids and digestates is of particular concern when these materials are applied to agricultural soils, as leaching and desorption processes can facilitate their transport into groundwater, while uptake by plants and soil biota further extends the risk of trophic transfer (Arvaniti et al., 2024; Lakshminarasimman et al., 2021).

Microplastics, often covered in biofilms, can adsorb pollutants, alter soil ecology, and enter the food chain, posing health risks to animals and humans, raising concerns over food security (Chang et al., 2022; Y. Wang et al., 2023). Recent studies revealed that the use of organic fertilizers, primarily derived from municipal waste and sewage sludge, has emerged as a notable pathway for microplastics to enter soil (L. Zhang et al., 2020). Research in digestates derived from biogenic waste treatment plants showed that plastic waste varied from 41 to 3298 particles kg^{-1} in raw digestate, 319-3604 particles kg^{-1} in solid digestate, and 7-38 particles kg^{-1} in liquid digestate (Yang et al., 2022).

Table 1 summarizes the main impurities and contaminants in digestate, their sources, fate during AD and environmental risks.

3.3. Environmental and regulatory challenges

The heterogeneous nature of digestate complicates the prediction of its environmental behaviour and hinders the establishment of uniform quality standards. When inadequately treated, digestate application may lead to nutrient runoff, eutrophication, greenhouse gas (GHGs) emissions, and the accumulation of heavy metals and emerging contaminants, including pharmaceuticals, ARGs, PFAS and microplastics. These pollutants can persist in soils and potentially enter groundwater or food chains, raising concerns about long-term ecosystem and human health impacts. Moreover, the absence of standardized analytical methodologies for emerging contaminants in digestate hampers consistent monitoring and risk evaluation across studies.

From a regulatory standpoint, progress remains fragmented. The EU Fertilising Products Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 defines digestate as a component material under certain nutrient and pathogen criteria, yet emerging pollutants and ARGs are still unregulated. National differences in contaminant thresholds, nutrient limits and end-of-waste classifications create further uncertainty, obstructing the formation of a unified European market for digestate-derived products. In parallel, several treatment options, such as drying, advanced oxidation and thermal conversion, are energy-intensive and may generate secondary waste streams requiring additional oversight. Bridging these gaps demands the development of harmonized contaminant standards, risk-based monitoring frameworks and clear end-of-waste criteria, complemented by supportive policies that encourage innovation and integrate life cycle and techno-economic assessments into regulatory decision-making. Such measures are crucial to ensure that digestate valorisation aligns with circular economy goals while maintaining environmental integrity and public safety.

Overcoming these environmental and regulatory constraints necessitates not only clearer policy frameworks but also the deployment of innovative treatment technologies capable of ensuring digestate stability, safety and resource recovery. The next section explores the current and emerging technological solutions developed to address these challenges, ranging from conventional separation and biological stabilization processes to advanced physicochemical and electrochemical methods, highlighting their mechanisms, maturity and potential for sustainable digestate valorisation.

Table 1
Main impurities and contaminants in digestate, their sources, fate during AD and risks.

Contaminant type	Main feedstock sources	Typical concentration range	Environmental concern	Fate during AD	Key reference
Pathogens (faecal coliforms, Salmonella)	Animal manure, sewage sludge	$10^2 - 10^6$ CFU g ⁻¹	Sanitary risk for soil, crops & humans	Partially reduced during AD, thermophilic AD (~55 °C) more effective than mesophilic	Harirchi et al. (2022)
Heavy metals (Pb, Ni, Cr, Cd, Hg, Cu, Zn)	OFMSW, sewage sludge, industrial co-substrates	~0.1 – 500 mg kg ⁻¹ (dry) depending on source and metal	Soil accumulation, phytotoxicity, food-chain transfer	Persist through AD (may concentrate in solid fraction)	Czatkowska et al. (2025)
Pharmaceuticals (antibiotics, NSAIDs, hormones, β -blockers)	Sewage sludge, livestock manure, hospital waste	$\mu\text{g L}^{-1} - \text{mg L}^{-1}$	Ecotoxicity, promotion of antibiotic resistance	Partial biodegradation during AD (40-77 % for some)	Martín et al. (2021)
Contaminants of emerging concern (caffeine, nicotine, acetaminophen, flame retardants, bisphenols)	Food waste, sewage sludge, greywater inputs	0.1 – 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$	Endocrine disruption, chronic aquatic toxicity	Often partially degraded; many CECs persist through AD or form transformation products	Robledo-Mahón et al. (2025)
PCDDs, PCBs, PAHs (legacy POPs)	Mixed municipal waste, sewage sludge, industrial residues	ng g ⁻¹ – $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$	Carcinogenic, mutagenic, bioaccumulative	Largely persistent; adsorb to solids and survive AD	Gomez-Rico et al. (2024)
Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) (e.g., PFOA, PFOS, PFHxS, Fluorotelomers)	Sewage sludge, urban and industrial wastes, paper mill sludge, and animal manures	1 – 8200 $\mu\text{g/kg}$	Persistence, bioaccumulation, phytotoxicity, leaching to groundwater, plant uptake	Poorly removed (<38 %); short-chain PFAS may increase	(Arvaniti et al., 2024; Lakshminarasimman et al., 2021; Munoz et al., 2022)
Microplastics & nanoplastics	OFMSW, sewage sludge, biogenic waste, food processing residues	$10^2 - 10^5$ particles L ⁻¹	Physical/chemical soil contamination; vectors for pollutants	Survive AD, fragment into smaller particles but not mineralize	(Robledo-Mahón et al., 2025; Wojnowska-Baryła et al., 2022)

4. Current and emerging digestate treatment technologies

Taking into account the above and valuing its necessity, digestate processing has been identified as a method to enhance digestate management and valorisation, considering at the same time certain criteria such as the reduction of operational costs or the production of higher-value end-products (Fuchs and Drogg, 2013). These end-products may include phosphorus-rich solid fractions, liquid fractions rich in ammonium, or different type of chars (Vaneckhaute et al., 2017).

4.1. Conventional processes

4.1.1. Mechanical separation

Common separation techniques include the screw press, centrifuge, and vibrating screen (Guan et al., 2024; Kovačić et al., 2022). Despite the established status of these technologies within the industry, each biogas plant must tailor their approach for separation technology in accordance with their unique operational requirements. This need for customization stems from various factors that influence their separation efficiency, including the type of AD substrates and the resulting characteristics of the digestate (Fuchs and Drogg, 2013). Despite being well-established, screw press and the decanter centrifuge continue to attract researchers' interest targeting mainly the separation efficiency, the energy consumption, the requirements in addition of chemicals to improve the separation, and the resulting products' quality.

Decanter centrifuges allow operational flexibility via adjustable bowl and feed speeds, with the auger's differential speed controlling material retention. Higher bowl speeds improve fine solid recovery but raise energy use. Screw presses rely on screen size and back pressure to control liquid removal, requiring careful balance with feedstock dry matter and feed rate to optimize performance, energy use, and prevent clogging or wear (Cathcart et al., 2023).

In a recent study, 175 cases of full-scale solid-liquid separation of digestate were observed. Their findings supported the hypothesis that the biogas plant feedstock quality influences digestate separation efficiency. Centrifugation was found to separate significantly more dry matter and total phosphorus compared to screw press, particularly in manure digestate, decreasing the dry matter concentration in the liquid fraction by 30 %. However, screw presses were more efficient in terms of

energy consumption consuming 4.5 times less energy compared to centrifuges (Carraro et al., 2024). On a related note, Guilayn et al. categorized different separation equipment into two performance-based groups, namely high and low, aiming to provide a valuable benchmarking resource for digestate separation processes and to enable more realistic forecasting of their performance. Their analysis showed that digestates originating from fibrous substrates, such as cow manure and silage, are predominantly treated using screw presses and generally exhibit lower separation efficiencies. In contrast, digestates derived from non-fibrous substrates, including sewage sludge, are more commonly processed using decanter centrifuges, which achieve substantially higher separation efficiencies. In particular, decanter centrifuges demonstrate markedly superior phosphorus separation, with reported efficiencies ranging from 51 to 71.5 %, compared to only 8.5-10.9 % for screw presses (Guilayn et al., 2019). Consequently, the solid fraction produced by decanter centrifugation is significantly more enriched in phosphorus, highlighting the strong influence of feedstock characteristics and equipment choice on nutrient partitioning during digestate separation (Cathcart et al., 2023).

Additives like polyaluminum chloride, epichlorohydrine-dimethylamine with ethylenediamine, and polyacrylamides enhance solid-liquid separation. High molecular weight, low-charge flocculants are most effective, maximizing turbidity and organic matter removal at low dosages, while high cationic charge destabilizes flocculation (van der Wal et al., 2023). Nonetheless, the use of chemical additives could increase digestate's phytotoxicity, likely attributed to aluminum content and elevated salinity from chemical addition (Beggio et al., 2022). Consequently, further investigation into the effects on soil-plant systems is necessary when considering agricultural use of solid fraction after separation with chemicals addition (Li et al., 2024).

With respect to cost, decanter centrifuges excel in phosphorus recovery, but screw presses are more cost-effective, with capital costs of 15,000–65,000 € versus 50,000–250,000 € for centrifuges, and operating costs up to five times lower per tonne of feedstock (Lyons et al., 2021).

While composting and drying are widely established post-separation stabilization pathways for the solid fraction of digestate (15-30 % solids), their reported benefits are highly context-dependent and often contingent on site-specific operational conditions (Tambone et al.,

2017). Composting is consistently highlighted for its ability to improve sanitation, stability, and agronomic value at relatively low reported costs (with reported processing costs of around 2.81 €-per tonne); however, cost figures and environmental performance are sensitive to scale, feedstock composition, and emission control measures, which are not always consistently reported across studies (Cesaro, 2021; Nowak et al., 2024).

Similarly, thermal drying offers clear advantages in terms of volume reduction, storability, and pathogen inactivation, yet its high energy demand and the risk of nitrogen losses through volatilization limit its overall sustainability unless waste heat recovery and efficient air treatment systems are in place (Salamat et al., 2022).

Solar drying presents a promising low-carbon alternative, particularly when combined with acidification (has shown up to 94 % ammonia and 72 % methane emission reduction yielding nutrient-rich organic fertilizer), but its applicability remains constrained by climatic conditions, land availability, and operational complexity (Morey et al., 2023; Wang and Yuan, 2024).

4.1.2. Membrane filtration

Membrane technologies play a pivotal role in digestate treatment, managing to enable the recovery of both nutrients and water. Their significance lies in the high separation efficiency and selectivity toward solids nutrients, and micropollutants, positioning them as key tools for resource-oriented digestate management. However, their performance and sustainability remain strongly dependent on membrane type, operating conditions, and pre-treatment strategies.

Hydraulically driven membrane processes comprise a broad group of technologies distinguished by operating pressure, pore size and membrane charge (Van Der Bruggen et al., 2003). This category includes widely applied processes such as microfiltration, ultrafiltration, nanofiltration and reverse osmosis, which are used at industrial scale for wastewater and digestate treatment. Several studies report near-complete removal of suspended solids using UF-based systems, with reductions of up to four orders of magnitude when treating cattle manure digestate (Guo and Jin, 2013; Waeger et al., 2010) and solid removal efficiencies exceeding 95 % when UF is combined with auxiliary filtration steps (Zhan et al., 2018).

For further purification or controlled disposal of the liquid fraction, NF and RO systems are used. NF membranes, with pore sizes as small as 1 nm, can retain micropollutants such as pharmaceuticals (Oussadou et al., 2025). Their separation mechanism is governed not only by size exclusion but also by electrostatic interactions arising from ionized functional groups on the membrane surface (Mohammad et al., 2015). As a result, NF shows strong rejection of multivalent anions such as phosphate, while most monovalent ions, including ammonium, largely pass into the permeate (Van Der Bruggen et al., 2003; Zacharof et al., 2019). This selective behaviour was demonstrated by Gerardo et al., who reported phosphate removal efficiencies of up to 97 % but ammonium removal of only 36 % during NF of dairy manure digestate across a wide pH range. Such disparities highlight the inherent limitations of NF for comprehensive nitrogen recovery (Gerardo et al., 2015).

RO systems have witnessed a significant surge in their utilization due to their ability to achieve near-complete retention of both nutrients and dissolved contaminants, with reported recovery rates of up to 99 % for phosphorus and nitrogen (Gong et al., 2013; Zhou et al., 2019). Nevertheless, these high separation efficiencies come at the expense of elevated operating pressures and energy demand, with reported treatment costs ranging between 4 and 12 €-per m³ of digestate (Rizzioli et al., 2023).

Membrane processes, while effective, face key limitations such as fouling. Fouling, caused by the accumulation of solids and organics on or within the membranes, poses significant challenges. It reduces permeate flux, degrades water quality, increases resistance and shortens membrane lifespan. A recent industrial-scale study on digestate treatment with polymeric UF membranes reported a lifespan of about 1 year. In

contrast, ceramic membranes operated for more than 1.5 years without any decline in flux or permeate quality, indicating that their active layer remained intact (Yfantis et al., 2022). While ceramic membranes offer improved robustness, their higher capital costs remain a barrier to widespread adoption (Rizzioli et al., 2023).

To mitigate fouling and enhance system performance, several studies emphasize the importance of effective pre-treatment (Chuda and Ziemiński, 2023; Y. Li et al., 2023). Centrifugation combined with coagulation or flocculation has been shown to substantially reduce fouling propensity and improve permeate quality. Notably, Chuda & Ziemiński demonstrated that UF preceded by centrifugation and either synthetic polyacrylamide or natural chitosan significantly improved filtration performance, supporting the potential substitution of synthetic chemicals with bio-based alternatives (Chuda and Ziemiński, 2023). Such approaches also contributed to the reduction of heavy metals and antibiotic residues, thereby improving the suitability of digestate-derived products for agricultural use (Li et al., 2023).

Process configuration also influences nutrient partitioning and concentrate management. UF systems incorporating intermittent back-flushing have been shown to reduce concentrate volumes (from 34 % to 12 % of the treated volume) while increasing phosphorus concentrations in the retentate, suggesting opportunities for targeted nutrient recovery (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024b). Additionally, under-stoichiometric ozonation has emerged as a promising strategy to enhance UF flux by 50-80 % without adversely affecting nutrient concentrations in fertilizer products, although its scalability and long-term impacts require further investigation (Gienau et al., 2020).

Despite their technical maturity and high separation efficiency, membrane processes remain constrained by high energy consumption, frequent cleaning requirements and material durability issues (Pérez et al., 2022). Moreover, pressure-driven membranes do not universally remove all contaminants, often necessitating additional treatment steps (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024c). The environmental footprint associated with chemical cleaning, membrane replacement and energy use further underscores the need for optimized system design. Future research should therefore focus on integrated process chains, harmonized performance metrics and life-cycle-based assessments to better define the role of membrane technologies within sustainable digestate management strategies.

4.1.3. Ammonia stripping

Ammonia stripping is a gas-liquid separation process designed to remove volatile compounds from liquid streams and is increasingly applied for nitrogen recovery from the liquid fraction of digestate. Reported nitrogen recovery efficiencies typically range between 80 and 90 %, with treatment costs of approximately 3-6 € per cubic meter of digestate, positioning stripping among the most cost-effective technologies for nitrogen extraction (Rizzioli et al., 2023).

The technology has reached commercial implementation, with full-scale installations such as the AMFER® system (Netherlands) and the Biogas Bree plant (Belgium) producing ammonium sulphate at industrial scale (AMFER, 2022; Biogas Bee, 2022). From a techno-economic standpoint, however, operational costs are strongly influenced by sulfuric acid prices and heat demand, making economic performance highly site-specific (Aravani et al., 2022). Revenue estimates of 90-120 € per tonne of digestate treated have been reported (Vaneekhaute et al., 2017), but these values depend on fertilizer market conditions, regulatory acceptance, and access to low-cost or waste heat. Consequently, while ammonia stripping performs favourably in terms of nitrogen recovery efficiency and unit treatment cost, its competitiveness relative to alternative nutrient recovery pathways remains contingent on local energy integration and market stability.

4.1.4. Chemical precipitation/crystallization

Chemical precipitation of phosphorus as magnesium or calcium phosphates represents one of the most established recovery routes from

digestate. Among these products, struvite ($\text{MgNH}_4\text{PO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) has attracted particular attention due to its stoichiometric incorporation of magnesium, ammonium and phosphate, and its suitability as a slow-release fertilizer with generally low levels of heavy metals and pathogens (Enyemadze et al., 2021; Kataki et al., 2016; Ma et al., 2018). Despite these favourable properties, the applicability of struvite precipitation to digestate streams is subject to several technical and economic limitations.

Struvite formation is highly sensitive to operational conditions, including pH, temperature, ion ratios, and hydrodynamics and is further complicated by the complex matrix of digestate. Suspended solids and colloidal material commonly present in digestate can adsorb onto growing crystals, disrupting crystal growth and reducing product purity. In addition, the typically high calcium content of digestate promotes the preferential formation of calcium phosphates, often at the expense of magnesium phosphate phases such as struvite (Corona et al., 2021). As a result, process performance is often less predictable than in conventional wastewater streams.

Although struvite precipitation has reached industrial application, reported recovery efficiencies and costs vary widely. Laboratory-scale optimization studies have demonstrated that under carefully controlled conditions (e.g., pH \sim 8.8, elevated magnesium dosing, and defined mixing regimes), nitrogen and phosphorus recovery efficiencies of up to 67 % and 81 %, respectively, can be achieved, alongside substantial cost reductions (Arellano-Yasaca et al., 2024). However, such optimized conditions may be difficult to maintain at full scale, particularly in decentralized biogas plants with variable digestate composition.

To overcome phosphorus binding in the solid fraction, acidification has been proposed as a pre-treatment strategy to enhance phosphorus solubilization prior to precipitation. Corona et al. demonstrated that acidification of manure-derived digestate increased phosphorus concentrations in the liquid fraction by up to 7.5 times, enabling recovery yields exceeding 95 % at pH 4.0 and improving overall precipitation efficiency for both struvite and calcium phosphate. Nevertheless, these gains must be weighed against the environmental and economic burdens associated with acid consumption, chemical handling and additional energy demand for pH adjustment, which may offset the benefits of increased recovery (Corona et al., 2021).

From a techno-economic perspective, struvite precipitation remains a cost-intensive recovery pathway, with reported production costs ranging from 270 to 2060 € per tonne, depending on scale, reagent prices and process configuration (Barampouti et al., 2020; Sengupta et al., 2015; Szymańska et al., 2019). While market prices for struvite can reach 600-2500 € per tonne, economic viability is strongly influenced by fertilizer market dynamics and the price of conventional mineral phosphorus sources (Barampouti et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2018). Consequently, although chemical precipitation offers a technically mature route for phosphorus recovery, its competitiveness relative to alternative pathways remains highly context-dependent and sensitive to both feedstock characteristics and external market conditions.

4.1.5. Ion exchange/sorption

Ion exchange techniques have been investigated for the recovery of nitrogen and phosphorus from wastewater and more recently, from digestate, using both natural and synthetic materials. Zeolites are among the most studied sorbents, with sodium- and potassium-based forms showing affinity for ammonium ions, while calcium-modified zeolites have been proposed for phosphate recovery (C. Chen et al., 2018; Hermassi et al., 2016; Montalvo et al., 2020).

The direct land application of nutrient-loaded zeolites has been suggested as an advantage of this approach, as it may bypass downstream processing steps (Cataldo et al., 2021; Flores et al., 2017; Montalvo et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2022; Soltys et al., 2020). However, evidence regarding the agronomic effectiveness of zeolite-based fertilizers remains fragmented. In particular, the fertilizer value and plant

availability of nutrients in mixed products containing zeolites and co-precipitated phases have not been systematically evaluated, limiting conclusions on their practical performance under field conditions.

Recent research has expanded sorption-based strategies by combining digestate with biochar to produce nutrient-enriched soil amenders. This approach exploits the porous structure and surface chemistry of biochar to adsorb nitrogen and phosphorus from the liquid fraction, effectively valorising two residual streams into a single product (Zheng et al., 2025b). This material has been shown to improve soil health by increasing soil organic matter and macronutrient content, with some studies showing a significant increase of 232-514 % in soil organic matter and 110-230 % in macronutrients compared to unenriched biochar (Kizito et al., 2019). In addition, nutrient-enriched biochar has been shown to mitigate environmental impacts associated with raw digestate, such as ammonia volatilization, odor emissions and nitrous oxide release (Manu et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2025a).

Despite these promising results, the sorption capacity of biochar is non-selective, raising concerns regarding the concurrent adsorption of contaminants such as pharmaceuticals and heavy metals present in digestate. The accumulation of these compounds may compromise the safety of biochar-based products for agricultural use and restrict regulatory acceptance. Furthermore, strategies for the regeneration, detoxification, or controlled disposal of spent biochar remain insufficiently developed, representing a key barrier to large-scale implementation (Ashiq et al., 2019; H.F. Chen et al., 2018).

Emerging research has also explored the use of nanomaterials for targeted contaminant removal from digestate, particularly heavy metals. Laboratory-scale studies have demonstrated high removal efficiencies using nanocomposite materials such as zinc oxide, graphene oxide, and silica-based systems (Khan et al., 2024). While these results highlight the technical potential of nanoparticle-based sorbents, their application remains at an early research stage. Key challenges include material costs, recovery and reuse of nanoparticles, potential ecotoxicological risks and the lack of full-scale demonstrations. Consequently, while ion exchange and sorption-based approaches offer flexibility and modularity, their role in digestate treatment remains largely complementary and requires further techno-economic and environmental validation before broader deployment.

4.2. Thermochemical and electrochemical routes

4.2.1. Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC)

Beyond conventional mechanical separation methods, thermal pretreatments have been investigated to enhance solid-liquid separation efficiency. An emerging technology for digestate dewaterability is hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) that is typically used for the conversion of organic biomass into hydrochar. HTC reduces hydrophilic functional groups in the biomass matrix, rendering hydrochars more hydrophobic and potentially facilitating water removal, which could reduce energy demand compared to drying untreated feedstock (Mikusińska et al., 2023).

Various types of digestate, including food waste (Yu et al., 2023), plant material (Pawlak-Kruczek et al., 2020), and sewage sludge (Aragón-Briceño et al., 2020), have been tested for HTC, with most studies focusing on producing hydrochar suitable for fuel applications (Pawlak-Kruczek et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2023). Combined HTC and pyrolysis has been proposed as a method to simultaneously reduce digestate volume and recover energy, with observations that HTC pretreatment can increase the heating value of both the digestate and the resulting pyrolytic char, as well as improve the degree of carbonization (Shi et al., 2023). The origin of the digestate and HTC operating conditions strongly influence the properties and yields of the resulting hydrochar, with energy crop digestates often producing higher hydrochar yields than manure- or food-based digestates (Cao et al., 2019).

Despite these promising results, most investigations remain at

laboratory or pilot scale and the scalability of HTC for digestate treatment remains uncertain. Critical issues include the management of the aqueous byproduct, which requires further treatment and the overall process complexity, which may limit applicability in existing biogas facilities. Reported levelized treatment costs range from 60 to 80 € per tonne of wet feedstock, with investment requirements around 351 € per tonne of annual capacity and operating expenses near € 20 per tonne, indicating a non-negligible economic burden (Aragón-Briceño et al., 2020; Ciceri et al., 2021; Medina-Martos et al., 2020). Environmental impacts of HTC, particularly the fate of nutrients and potential emissions from the liquid fraction, are still poorly quantified.

4.2.2. Pyrolysis

Pyrolysis, a thermal decomposition process occurring in an oxygen-free setting, yields diverse products such as char, bio-oil, and gases (Shi et al., 2023). This approach has been proposed for digestate treatment as a means to maximize resource recovery and minimize waste, converting organic residues into energy carriers and recyclable materials. Recent studies have investigated pyrolysis performances using digestates derived from various sources such as food waste (M. Liu et al., 2020), agricultural and animal waste (An et al., 2024), sewage sludge (Wang et al., 2024) and the OFMSW (H. Wen et al., 2021).

Despite its technical potential, several limitations constrain the application of pyrolysis to digestate streams. The high-water content of digestate presents a critical challenge, as it reduces the efficiency of thermal conversion, increases energy demand and complicates transport and handling. Moreover, most current studies remain at laboratory or pilot scale, with limited data on process integration, energy balances and the management of byproducts such as aqueous fractions and off gases.

4.2.3. Electrochemical systems

Electrochemical and bioelectrochemical systems are emerging as a sustainable method for recovering nutrients like nitrogen and phosphorus from digestate. These systems use electricity to drive the electromigration of ions, separating nutrients from the waste stream (Tsai et al., 2025). For example, a microbial electrochemical system (MES) was shown to recover over 60 % of ammonia nitrogen from anaerobic digester centrate with an energy consumption of 2.7 kWh per kg of nitrogen recovered (Liu et al., 2022). Comparable technologies report varying energy demands, such as 14.6 kWh per kg nitrogen for a concurrent nutrient recovery system (Z. Wang et al., 2023) and approximately 3.6 to 3.7 kWh per kg nitrogen for another electrochemical approach (Carucci et al., 2022), values that remain competitive relative to conventional nutrient recovery methods.

A notable technology, the electrochemical phosphorus recovery cell (EPRC), operates by anodic acidification to leach phosphorus, which subsequently precipitates in the cathode chamber (Carucci et al., 2022). These electrochemical technologies offer advantages including operational flexibility, low chemical input requirements, and favourable energy efficiency (Carucci et al., 2022). Economic assessments have reported recovery costs of approximately \$1.84 per kilogram of nitrogen and \$0.69 per kilogram of phosphorus, accompanied by preliminary profit margins exceeding 300 % when simultaneous nitrogen and phosphorus recovery is achieved (Wang et al., 2023).

Despite these strengths, challenges remain in the application of bioelectrochemical systems to digestate treatment. Treatment efficacy tends to decline when transitioning from synthetic wastewater models to complex real-world digestate matrices, adversely affecting nitrogen removal performance (Carucci et al., 2022). Moreover, post-recovery processing is often necessary, phosphorus recovery typically requires additional chemical precipitation steps, whereas ammonia recovery may involve further techniques such as air stripping or membrane contactors to achieve desired purity and usability (Wang et al., 2023).

4.2.4. Electrodialysis

The electrodialysis (ED) process is an emerging technology for

nutrient recovery from digestate and has gained significant attention in recent years (Pan et al., 2025). Previous studies have proved that digestate can be condensed into a valuable bio-nutrient product with conventional ED systems. This process not only aids in enhancing the value of digestate but also reduces transportation costs by decreasing the water content in the concentrated digestate.

Through employing selective membranes and positioning them in proper configurations selective extraction of nutrient ions from digestate into separate streams could be achieved. Ye et al. studied nutrient fractionation from synthetic swine manure digestate, managing to separate all divalent cations, multivalent anions, and monovalent ions into three separate products. This innovation could reduce the need of an external source of magnesium, which often contributes 50-75 % of the overall costs in established struvite recovery processes (Ye et al., 2019). This system was also studied with digestate derived from sewage sludge showing promising results for nutrient ions separation and pharmaceutical compounds (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024a).

Advanced configurations, such as bipolar membrane ED, further allow the generation of acidic and alkaline streams from digestate, yielding higher-value products compared to conventional salt recovery. Reported recoveries include up to 78 % ammonium, 75 % phosphate, and 78 % volatile fatty acids from manure digestate, with recent optimizations reducing energy demand by ~32 % (Shi et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2023).

However, practical deployment faces several challenges. Nutrient recovery, particularly phosphorus, is often lower in real digestates compared to synthetic feeds due to phosphorus binding to organic molecules that cannot permeate the membranes. Reported phosphorus recoveries from real digestates vary widely, from 5 to 78 %, depending on feedstock and treatment conditions (Ebberts et al., 2015; Guedes et al., 2015; Oliveira et al., 2018; V. Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024).

Membrane fouling remains a critical constraint, necessitating pre-treatment and ongoing maintenance. Techniques such as periodic reversal of the applied potential have been shown to mitigate fouling and improve separation, but optimal operating parameters are highly system- and feedstock-dependent (Shi et al., 2018). Other operational concerns include electrode degradation, system complexity, and elevated maintenance costs, which together affect long-term sustainability and techno-economic feasibility.

4.3. Advanced and hybrid approaches

4.3.1. Membrane-based treatment trains

Research in this area has consistently shown that membrane processes have such a wide range of applications that one can design a complete digestate separation/purification system solely using membrane processes (Adam et al., 2018; Chiumenti et al., 2013; Gerardo et al., 2015; Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024, 2024b, 2024c; Yfantis et al., 2022; Zacharof et al., 2019). A typical configuration involves MF, which can supplement or replace centrifugation for suspended solids removal, followed by UF to further reduce solids and recover phosphorus, and finally NF or RO for nutrient concentration and high-quality water recovery. Such systems can reclaim up to ~50 % of water from digestate, with concentrates potentially valorised into fertilizers or soil amendments if properly managed. Fig. 1 presents an integrated membrane system comprising pressure-driven and electrochemically-driven membranes for whole digestate valorisation.

Laboratory and pilot-scale studies highlight both the potential and constraints of this approach. For instance, Qi et al. demonstrated a combination of UF and RO for swine manure digestate, achieving 90 % water recovery and producing water suitable for discharge or reuse. However, nitrogen and phosphorus were not efficiently recovered, limiting the system's ability to fully valorise all nutrients. The recovered fractions were primarily potassium, calcium, magnesium, and humic acids, suitable for water-soluble fertilizer production, illustrating the selectivity limitations of integrated membrane systems (Qi et al., 2021).

Fig. 1. Integrated membrane system comprising pressure-driven and electrochemically-driven membranes for digestate valorisation. Membrane concentrate streams may serve as soil amenders, provided contaminant levels are sufficiently low.

Other studies have explored dual processing pathways based on feedstock pH. Acidic treatments combining centrifugation, MF, and forward osmosis (FO) produced nutrient-rich liquid fertilizers, recovering ~46 % of water and less than 50 % of nutrients, whereas alkaline pathways employing membrane contactor-based stripping achieved higher nutrient recovery (e.g., ~81 % nitrogen, ~100% phosphorus, ~83 % potassium) and 75 % water recovery as irrigation water (Rodríguez-Alegre et al., 2023). While these results indicate substantial valorisation potential, they also reveal the complexity and trade-offs inherent in fully integrated membrane-based systems: water recovery may come at the expense of certain nutrients and feedstock chemistry, pH and process configuration strongly influence the composition and usability of final products.

Despite these promising outcomes, the practical implementation of integrated membrane systems remains largely untested at industrial scale. Challenges include membrane fouling, high energy demand, system complexity, maintenance requirements, and the need for pre-treatment to protect sensitive downstream membranes. Moreover, current studies often lack comprehensive life cycle assessments and techno-economic analyses, which are essential to evaluate energy efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and environmental impact under real-world operating conditions. Consequently, while integrated membrane systems offer a highly modular and technically feasible approach for digestate valorisation, further pilot- and full-scale demonstrations are required to assess their scalability, economic viability and true sustainability potential.

4.3.2. Advanced approaches for pharmaceutical removal

As highlighted previously, an increasing number of studies are addressing the occurrence of pharmaceuticals, particularly antibiotics, in waste streams and their subsequent release into the environment. The effective removal of these compounds from digestate is critical to interrupt their environmental cycle and to prevent their transfer to soils and ultimately to surface and groundwater resources. Membrane systems have been extensively studied for the removal of such compounds from wastewater. Techniques such as UF, NF, and RO have also demonstrated high efficiency in removing antibiotics from liquid fraction of digestate (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024c; Yue et al., 2020).

However, antibiotics may not be degraded through membrane separation alone resulting in membranes' concentrates, necessitating additional measures such as pyrolysis or advanced oxidation for their degradation (Proskynitopoulou et al., 2024b; Yue et al., 2020).

Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) generate highly oxidizing hydroxyl radicals through methods such as ozonation (Ma et al., 2023), UV coupled with ozonation or hydrogen peroxide (Moradi et al., 2024), Fenton oxidation (Thomas et al., 2021), photolysis (Cheng and Hong, 2017), and electrochemical oxidation are also examined for pharmaceuticals removal from digestate. A key advantage of AOPs is their ability to achieve very high removal efficiencies for a wide spectrum of persistent contaminants. Wang et al. reported tetracycline, oxytetracycline and chlortetracycline removals of 89-96 % under optimized photocatalytic conditions. Despite this, practical application in digestate is limited by high energy and chemical requirements, potential formation of toxic by-products and reduced performance in complex matrices where organic matter scavenges hydroxyl radicals (Moradi et al., 2023; Wang and Yuan, 2021a). These limitations raise concerns about scalability and economic feasibility in full-scale biogas plant operations.

Bioelectrochemical systems (BES), including microbial fuel cells (MFC) and microbial electrolysis cells (MEC), have emerged as an alternative for antibiotic degradation. In these systems, anodic microorganisms oxidize contaminants while generating electricity or hydrogen (Wang and Zhuan, 2020; Yang et al., 2022). Removal efficiency depends on operational conditions, such as applied voltage, and can be further enhanced by coupling BES with adsorption or AOPs to improve energy efficiency and reduce costs (Wu et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2018). Constructed wetland-based BES setups have achieved antibiotic removal rates up to 99 % (Li et al., 2018; Y. Wen et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2018), although their mechanisms, full-scale feasibility, and economic performance remain underexplored.

Fig. 2 depicts a digestate valorisation process train for simultaneous nutrient and antibiotics removal. This process integrates a membrane system coupled with ozone for better filtration performance and oxidation of antibiotics, while the UF permeate is further treated with BES for nutrient recovery and further antibiotics oxidation.

Overall, while membrane-based and bioelectrochemical approaches offer high removal potential, their real-world applicability is

Fig. 2. Digestate valorisation process train with simultaneous nutrient and antibiotics removal.

constrained by matrix complexity, residual toxicity, energy consumption and operational costs. Integrated process trains, combining membranes with AOPs and BES, represent a promising strategy to simultaneously recover nutrients and remove pharmaceuticals, but further pilot- and full-scale studies are needed to assess long-term performance, environmental impact and techno-economic viability.

4.3.3. PFAS management in digestate

While the environmental and health risks of PFAS and other emerging contaminants are increasingly recognized, comprehensive review papers addressing their removal from complex matrices like digestate remain notably scarce.

The current approach to managing PFAS in digestate is largely defined by the limitations of existing technologies. While physical

separation technologies like granular activated carbon (GAC), ion exchange resins and membrane filtration can effectively remove PFAS from liquid streams, they do not offer a complete solution (Tajdini et al., 2025; Woodard et al., 2017). Their primary function is to concentrate the contaminants into a smaller, secondary waste stream which then requires costly and energy-intensive disposal, typically through high-temperature incineration. Destructive technologies that can break the resilient carbon-fluorine bond, such as thermal processes and advanced oxidation, show promise but face significant hurdles in cost, scalability and the risk of creating toxic byproducts if combustion is incomplete (Li et al., 2023; Meegoda et al., 2022; Protection Agency, 2024). A critical gap remains in the absence of a single, cost-effective technology that can manage PFAS within the complex solid matrix of digestate, further complicated by a lack of standardized analytical

Table 2

Mapping of major contaminant groups in digestate to suitable treatment technologies and key mechanisms.

Contaminant group	Main effective technologies	Mechanism/fate	TRL	Remaining challenges	Key references
Pharmaceuticals	AOPs, BES, filtration, thermal or hydrothermal destruction, composting, adsorption	Oxidative degradation → CO ₂ + H ₂ O	4-8	High operating costs Formation of transformation products, Matrix complexity and variability Concentrate management High cost	(Luo et al., 2023; Wang and Zhuan, 2020; Wang and Yuan, 2021b)
Antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs)	AOPs, BES, filtration, thermal or hydrothermal destruction, composting, adsorption	DNA denaturation/ oxidative cleavage	3-9	Limited ARG removal efficiency Uncertainty in ARG fate Matrix effects High cost	(Ji et al., 2012; Li et al., 2018; Sanz et al., 2021)
PFAS	Adsorption, ion exchange, thermal or hydrothermal destruction	Mineralization to CO ₂ + F ⁻	5-9	Complex matrix Formation of toxic byproducts High pressure and temperature requirements High operational costs	Meegoda et al. (2022)
Heavy metals	Precipitation, sorption to biochar or zeolite, selective leaching	Immobilization or separation	3-9	Metal-rich sludge production as byproduct Presence of competing ions and dissolved organic matter High consumption of chemicals Energy cost	(Chu et al., 2020; Ebberts et al., 2015; Salud Camilleri-Rumbau et al., 2019; Shen et al., 2016)
Microplastics/nanoplastics	Coagulation, sedimentation, flotation, filtration, thermal or hydrothermal destruction	Physical removal or destruction	4-9	Poor removal Secondary pollution from chemical coagulants By-products Plastics not fully mineralized Energy-intensive	(Akaniro et al., 2024; Carnevale Miino et al., 2024; X. X. Zhang et al., 2020)

methods to accurately measure contamination in solids.

Looking forward, the most viable prospect for managing PFAS-contaminated digestate appears to be a multi-stage treatment approach that integrates highly efficient separation technologies with a final, robust destruction method (Scheitlin et al., 2023). This strategy focuses on minimizing the volume of hazardous material before applying energy-intensive destruction, potentially making the process more economically feasible. However, the most effective long-term prospect lies not in end-of-pipe treatment but in upstream source control. Future progress will depend on a coordinated effort to advance these integrated systems, accelerate research into scaling destructive technologies like hydrothermal processing, and, most importantly, enact

policies that prioritize pollution prevention at the source.

To illustrate the relationship between digestate contaminants and treatment options, Table 2 provides a mapping of major contaminant groups to suitable treatment technologies, along with their key removal mechanisms.

5. Technology readiness and performance assessment

The wide range of technologies applied to digestate management, spanning physical, chemical, biological, and thermochemical processes, are currently at varying stages of technological maturity. Evaluating TRLs provides a structured approach to determine their development

Table 3

Summary of technological readiness, typical performance, and sustainability metrics for key digestate treatment and nutrient recovery technologies.

Technology	Main objective	TRL	Typical N recovery (%)	Typical P recovery (%)	Energy demand	OPEX (€/m ³)	Key environmental aspects	Main limitations	Reference
Screw press/ decanter centrifuge	Volume reduction, partial nutrient partitioning	8-9	10-30 (mainly to liquid fraction)	60-80 (retained in solid fraction)	0.4-5 kWh m ⁻³	0.08-1.2	Main burden is polymer use Minor energy impact	Limited nutrient recovery High volume of liquid fraction that requires handling	(Feiz et al., 2022; Nowak and Czekala, 2024)
Ultrafiltration (UF)	Volume reduction, particle and colloid removal	6-8	70-90	50-70	2.3-15 kWh m ⁻³	0.5-5	Moderate energy consumption Concentrate management Cleaning chemicals	Fouling & scaling Membrane replacement	(Gienau et al., 2018; Mancuso et al., 2024; Yue et al., 2022; Zielińska and Bułkowska, 2025)
Nanofiltration (NF)	Volume reduction, N, K, P concentration	5-6	70-95	40-60	5-12 kWh m ⁻³	1.5-7	Moderate energy consumption Concentrate management Cleaning chemicals	Fouling & scaling Membrane replacement Digestate requires pretreatment	(Adam et al., 2018; Mancuso et al., 2024; Rizzioli et al., 2025)
Reverse osmosis (RO)	Volume reduction, water recovery	7-8	80-95	<20	6-15 kWh m ⁻³	1.36-10	High energy demand Concentrate management Cleaning chemicals	Fouling & scaling Membrane replacement Digestate requires pretreatment	(Gienau et al., 2018; Mancuso et al., 2024)
Electrodialysis (ED) Selective/ Bipolar/ Reverse	Ion separation Production of base and acid	5-6	60-90	40-60	11.6-15.2 kWh/kg NH ₃ recovered	15-25	Concentrate management Cleaning chemicals	Fouling & scaling Membrane replacement Digestate requires pretreatment Products require further treatment	(Anwar et al., 2025; Kovačić et al., 2022)
Ammonia stripping	N recovery as ammonium sulphate	7-9	70-95	-	1-5 kWh kg N ⁻¹	2-5	Moderate energy demand Acid and base use	Requires heating Odor control pH control	Kovačić et al. (2022)
Precipitation	P recovery	8-9	10-20	70-95	0.5-1 kWh m ⁻³	1-3	Energy and chemical use	Reagent cost Product purity	Kovačić et al. (2022)
Hydrothermal carbonization (HTC)	Carbon stabilization Contaminants removal	4-6	50-70 (in liquor)	70-90 (in hydrochar)	500-800 kWh t ⁻¹ DS	15-40 €/t	Potential C-negative High energy use By-products management	Energy cost By-products handling	Abdelfatah-Aldayyat et al. (2024)
Pyrolysis	Energy recovery Contaminants removal	5-7	20-40	60-90	400-700 kWh t ⁻¹ DS	20-50 €/t	GWP benefit if biochar applied to soil Lower GWP than incineration	Emission control Fouling Operational issues	Garlapalli et al. (2016)
AOPs	Contaminants oxidation	3-5	-	-	0.15-0.75 kWh/m ⁻³	-	High energy demand Chemicals addition	Usually requires pretreatment Electrode stability High cost	Moradi et al. (2024)

status and identify research and investment priorities. Most conventional separation and stabilization processes (e.g., centrifugation, filtration, composting) have reached commercial maturity (TRL 8-9) and are routinely implemented in full-scale biogas plants. In contrast, advanced membrane systems, HTC, pyrolysis, and AOPs are generally at pilot to demonstration stages (TRL 4-7), with ongoing optimization of process integration, energy demand and operational stability. Bio-electrochemical and microbial electrolysis systems remain at laboratory scale (TRL 3-5), limited by low current densities, sensitivity to feed variability, and high capital costs (Table 3).

Performance assessment across technologies highlights trade-offs between removal efficiency, resource recovery and environmental footprint. While membrane and electrochemical processes achieve high nutrient and water recovery, they often generate secondary waste streams (concentrates) requiring further management. Thermal and AOP-based methods effectively destroy persistent contaminants such as antibiotics and PFAS but are constrained by high energy consumption

and potential formation of toxic by-products. Furthermore, integrated or hybrid systems that combine separation, concentration and destructive steps, for example, UF-RO coupled with AOP or HTC, show the greatest promise for balancing efficiency with environmental sustainability. To support large-scale deployment, future assessments should incorporate techno-economic (TEA) and life-cycle analyses (LCA) under harmonized assumptions, enabling fair comparison between emerging and established technologies. This integrated evaluation framework is essential for guiding research, investment and policy decisions toward sustainable digestate valorisation.

6. Integration and valorisation pathways

Each digestate valorisation case is inherently unique and must therefore be evaluated individually. Owing to the significant fluctuation in digestate composition, each case presents specific challenges that must be addressed to identify the most appropriate treatment strategy.

Fig. 3. Decision framework for selecting digestate treatment and nutrient recovery pathways based on feedstock characterization, contaminant fingerprint and valorisation objectives.

In practice, multiple treatment methods and process configurations often need to be combined to maximize the valorisation potential of a given digestate and to mitigate or eliminate technical, environmental, or regulatory constraints.

This inherent heterogeneity underscores the need for a structured decision framework that can support the transition of anaerobic digestion from a waste-treatment process to a circular biorefinery model. Such a framework must explicitly link the high variability of digestate composition to differentiated valorisation objectives. Most existing decision-support approaches for digestate or wastewater management typically optimize individual unit operations (e.g., nutrient recovery efficiency, energy balance, or cost minimization) in isolation. In contrast, the proposed framework adopts a feedstock-driven, risk-based logic, in which the contaminant fingerprint of the incoming material is treated as the primary decision variable, determining both the sequencing and admissibility of downstream technologies rather than being addressed as a secondary constraint.

As illustrated in Fig. 3, the decision logic follows a stepwise structure:

1. Feedstock typology: Initial characterization of organic loading, nutrient ratios, and physical state.
2. Contaminant screening: Identifying “Red flag” constituents (heavy metals, PFAS, microplastics, pharmaceuticals).
3. Primary objective setting: Defining the goal (e.g., maximum P-recovery vs. volume reduction).
4. Pathway selection: Matching the material to the most resilient technology train.

The process begins with comprehensive feedstock characterization, e.g., quantifying solids, nutrient profiles and contaminant burdens, to define the primary management goal such as nutrient recovery, volume reduction and water reuse, or contaminant removal. For example, digestates from agricultural residues typically pose low contaminant risk, while those from OFMSW or sewage sludge require precautionary treatment trains to avoid contaminant accumulation in fertilizers or soil improvers.

Once objectives are established, resource screening determines site feasibility and cost-effectiveness. The availability of thermal energy from CHP units, chemical reagents (e.g., acids for stripping) and market demand for recovered products (e.g., struvite, ammonium sulphate, soil amenders) are decisive. Energy-intensive processes, such as RO (8-15 kWh m⁻³) or HTC (500-800 kWh t⁻¹ DS), are therefore positioned as conditional options, suitable only where waste heat or favourable energy integration is available. In contrast, emerging systems such as bipolar electrodialysis (TRL 5-6) are highlighted for their potential to improve long-term economic resilience by generating acids and bases in situ, thereby reducing exposure to chemical price volatility.

The initial solid-liquid separation step is treated as a critical decision point, as it largely determines contaminant partitioning and downstream flexibility. As aforementioned, a decanter centrifuge (TRL 8-9) retains 51-71 % of phosphorus in the solid fraction but entails high capital and energy demand. Conversely, a screw press (TRL 8-9), while less efficient in phosphorus capture, is approximately four times less energy intensive. Depending on the selected separation technology and characterisation profile, appropriate options for further treatment of the liquid digestate should be considered.

Following this split, treatment paths diverge according to resource focus:

- Pathway A (Solids-rich, high-P streams): composting, drying, or thermal valorisation (HTC, pyrolysis) for stable soil amenders and carbon retention.
- Pathway B (Liquid, nutrient-rich streams): membrane systems, stripping, or crystallization processes for N, P, and K recovery.
- Pathway C (High-purity water goal): advanced membrane systems (NF/RO) coupled with concentrate management.

- Pathway D (Contaminant destruction): membrane systems for concentration of contaminants in specific streams, AOPs and thermal treatment for contaminated digestate streams

To illustrate practical application, two contrasting scenarios highlight how the decision framework guides the selection of treatment pathways according to feedstock characteristics, contaminant levels, regulatory requirements and recovery objectives. Digestate management must remain adaptable, as agricultural residues and urban-derived substrates present very different risks and resource opportunities.

Scenario 1 The “Clean” loop (agricultural residues)

- Logic: Low contaminant risk allows for a “low-intensity” path.
- Process: Screw press → Struvite precipitation → Composting.
- Outcome: High-volume recycling to land with minimal OPEX.

Scenario 2 The “Precautionary” loop (sewage sludge/OFMSW)

- Logic: High risk of POPs and metals.
- Process: Centrifugation (to concentrate pollutants in solids) → HTC of solids → Advanced membrane treatment of liquid.
- Outcome: Complete destruction of pathogens/POPs while reclaiming energy and purified water.

Finally, system integration is essential to close loops: heat recovery from CHP units, recirculation of treated effluents to anaerobic digestion, and blending of biochar or concentrates into stabilized solids improve overall efficiency and circularity. Each configuration must undergo TEA and LCA to ensure that energy-intensive or low-TRL innovations deliver net environmental and economic benefits.

7. Remaining challenges and research directions

This review highlights the remarkable variability of digestate, driven by feedstock type and anaerobic digestion conditions, which results in diverse nutrient profiles and contaminant levels. A range of treatment strategies, from nutrient recovery to contaminant mitigation, offers pathways to manage these differences effectively. Thus, integrated valorisation frameworks that align feedstock analysis, tailored processing, and end-use goals can convert digestate into safe, high-value soil amendments, advancing circular economy principles and sustainable agriculture.

Despite recent progress in digestate treatment and valorisation, several key challenges continue to constrain its environmental performance and market deployment. The main barriers relate to heterogeneous digestate composition, limited process standardization, and fragmented regulatory frameworks, which together hinder the comparability, scalability, and economic feasibility of treatment solutions. Addressing these issues requires not only technological innovation but also harmonized policy support and robust monitoring systems (Fig. 4).

From a policy perspective, priority actions include the harmonization of digestate quality standards across the EU Fertilising Products Regulation (FPR), national Animal By-Product (ABP) rules, and bio-fertilizer certification schemes to enable cross-border product trade. Establishing concentration-management limits for concentrate streams (e.g., RO or ED) analogous to sludge land-spreading rules can help prevent secondary pollution. Moreover, the development of analytical guidelines for PFAS, pharmaceuticals, and ARGs, covering detection limits, is essential for consistent monitoring. Fiscal incentives rewarding verified nitrogen and phosphorus recovery and integration of digestate valorisation into broader soil-health and nutrient-management policies would further promote market uptake and circularity.

In parallel, research and innovation efforts should focus on pilot- and demonstration-scale validation of hybrid membrane and

Policy priorities

Harmonize digestate quality standards across EU to enable cross-border product trade.

Adopt concentration-management limits for concentrates to avoid secondary pollution.

Establish analytical guidelines for PFAS, pharmaceuticals, and ARGs in digestate.

Promote fiscal incentives for N and P recovery proportional to verified circularity or CO₂ savings.

Integrate digestate valorisation into soil-health and nutrient-management policies, linking with the Soil Mission and Circular Economy Action Plan.

Research and innovation gaps

Advance pilot-scale trials (TRL 6→8) for integrated technologies treating real digestate.

Develop LCA and TEA databases under harmonized assumptions for comparison of emerging vs mature technologies.

Design PFAS-specific destruction technology trains optimized for digestate.

Investigate long-term agronomic impacts and contaminant transfer from digestate-derived fertilizers.

Digitalize monitoring and traceability for nutrient-recovery products to improve public trust and regulatory compliance.

Fig. 4. Policy and research priorities for sustainable digestate valorisation.

electrochemical systems (e.g., ED-ammonia stripping) treating real digestate streams. Furthermore, targeted development of PFAS-specific destruction technology trains and long-term assessment of agronomic and contaminant-transfer impacts from digestate-derived fertilizers remain high priorities. Establishing harmonized LCA and TEA databases will allow fair comparison between emerging and mature technologies. Finally, the digitalization of monitoring and traceability through Internet of Things (IoT) and blockchain technologies can improve public trust, product certification, and regulatory compliance. Collectively, these actions define a roadmap toward sustainable, transparent, and circular digestate valorisation.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vera Proskynitopoulou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anastasios Vourros:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ioannis Garagounis:** Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Souzana Lorentzou:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration. **Anastasios Zouboulis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Kyriakos Panopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration.

Funding

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme through the project Waste4Soil (GA101112708).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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